

About Journal

The Rubrics (ISSN 2454-1974) is a peer-reviewed, international, online Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies. It is published bi-monthly in an open access by Magnus Publishing. The main objective of the journal is to encourage scholars to undertake research leading to sustainable development across disciplines. The Rubrics Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies invite authors from all over the world to submit original and innovative research manuscripts with interdisciplinary approach for consideration in the areas such as:

Anthropology, Communication Studies, Governance, Cross-cultural Studies, Demography, Education, Ethics, Geography, History, Industrial Relations, Information Science, International Relations, Law, Library Science, Media Studies, Philosophy, Political Science, Population Studies, Psychology, Public Administration, Sociology and Science.

Above areas are suggestive only, you may choose a topic of your own interest within the scope of the Journal. Unpublished manuscripts not currently under consideration by any other publisher are invited from scholars. Research students are encouraged to submit manuscripts for consideration through research supervisor. We accept unsolicited book reviews, data reports and conference reports for publication.

Aims and Scope

The Rubrics Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies (ISSN 2454-1974) aims to encourage scholars to undertake research leading to sustainable development across disciplines. The Rubrics is theory and research-oriented journal that encourages original research, case studies and methods, data reports, datasets, review manuscripts, conceptual frameworks, analytical models, technical notes, and book reviews. The Rubrics highly promotes research across disciplines and encourage scholars to contribute innovative results to the existing knowledge base.

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